

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF USE OF LEADERSHIP STYLES IN
MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

In this article, the essence of leadership styles in management psychology, the manifestation of leadership styles in the activities of management system leaders, the psychological aspects of the use of leadership styles, Frederic Winslow Taylor's ideas about the nine qualities characteristic of an ideal management employee, and Henri Fayol's information about the qualities based on Taylor's opinion are highlighted. information, the essence of leadership styles and the methods of use are mentioned.

Key words: management psychology, leadership personality, management activity, authoritarian, democratic, liberal leadership styles.

Introduction. Our historical and daily experience shows that some managers are more effective than others. Why does this happen? What characteristics or aspects of the performance of an effective manager differ from others?

The answer to these questions is subject to huge commercial changes in the development of management theory.

The foundations of the first psychological theories of scientific management were based on their own experiences and observations, and they distinguished the social and psychological qualities that a manager should have in order to carry out his activities effectively.

For example, Frederick Winslow Taylor showed nine qualities of an ideal manager. They are: intelligence, knowledge, special professional knowledge, physical agility or strength, restraint, enthusiasm, determination, honesty, judgment and common sense, strength and health.

Henri Fayol also singled out the qualities of this management employee, such as those mentioned by Taylor: health and physical strength, intelligence and mental work ability, firm will, activity, enthusiasm, courage, willingness to take responsibility, sense of duty, concern for the common good, a wide range of general knowledge, the ability to develop an action program and organize its development, the ability to organize joint work, the ability to manage people, the ability to coordinate actions, control skills, general education, gaining deeper professional knowledge. Both lists of qualities listed above are the product of experience and intelligence, not specific research.

The main part. Attempts to provide a scientific answer to the question of the qualities of an effective manager were first made in the 30s of the 20th century from the point of view known as "trait theory". According to the essence of this theory, the most effective managers have a certain set of personal qualities that are common to all. It is not difficult to see that this rule is consistent with the opinions of Frederick Taylor and Henri Fayol.

While thinking about leadership styles in the field of management, it is necessary to emphasize that in the works of the President, he also talks about the responsibility of the leader, his in-depth knowledge of his management activities, qualifications, and experience. Detailed

comments were made. It is permissible to turn the expressed opinions into an action program for every leader in his daily work. In fact, since the field of management is an extremely complex and diverse process, it is permissible to go deeper into it. President Sh.Mirziyoyev emphasized the responsibility and duty of leadership and expressed the following opinions: "The implementation of the tasks set for 2017 and beyond is crucially dependent on the three most important requirements.

The first requirement is the personal responsibility of the leaders at all levels, starting with the head of state - the President, for the final results;

The second requirement is to ensure clear order and strict discipline in all spheres. I emphasize once again that we will do the work together, and each of us will be personally responsible for the result.

The third requirement is to ensure the purity of our ranks and personnel, to prevent any negative situations at work and to root out such vices. [1]

Summarizing the literature related to the field of management, it is said that in many cases, effective management employees are distinguished by their intelligence, knowledge, responsibility, activity, reliability, and participation in social life, but they have demonstrated these qualities in various situations. we can conclude. Another important thing is that a person does not become a manager just because he has a certain set of personal qualities, that is, there are no personal qualities associated with the effectiveness of a person's work as a manager. Just as the absence of any quality in a person does not inevitably lead to failure, neither intelligence nor determination is a guarantee of success. Therefore, during the attestation of management personnel, such descriptions as "Honest, always ready to help, demanding" and similar descriptions written in their recommendation letters only provide information about the personal qualities of the person undergoing attestation, but the enumeration of such qualities, does not provide a basis for concluding what kind of management employee he is.

Unsuccessful attempts to identify the characteristics of effective management personnel led to the emergence of a new approach in the field of management focused on the employee's personal qualities and his behavior. It is not important what special qualities a management employee has, but how he behaves towards subordinates, his management characteristics, and management styles are important. It was this idea that turned out to be more useful.

In the development of management psychology, several approaches to the management style have emerged, and it has been established that there is a connection between the management employee's method of activity and the team's effectiveness.

Management style is a relatively stable system of practical behavior determined by the methods of solving the tasks of the employee of the management field.

One of the important characteristics of the style is how the manager involves subordinates in the decision-making process. The degree of freedom given to subordinates can vary from the lowest to the highest. Within this approach, three styles of management are distinguished: authoritarian, democratic and liberal.

In an **autocratic style**, a manager always makes decisions without consulting subordinates, such leaders make their own judgments and do not allow employees to take initiative. He wants to have a relationship with his subordinates that unconditionally accepts all the orders of the leader. An authoritarian leader is detached from the team and always keeps subordinates away from him. For this leader, subordinates are only executors. In the activities of representatives of this style,

the administrative method always prevails, that is, orders, punishments, deprivation of certain privileges. He recognizes only two ways of directing employees to work. These two ways are financial incentives for employees and administrative punishment.

Such a manager usually talks to his subordinates privately, in which the tone of command prevails, and he does not tolerate the objections and criticism of his subordinates.

An authoritarian manager is self-confident and believes that employees do not have enough knowledge to participate in management, even when they want to help the manager, they perceive any help as "interference" in their management activities, and they are easily distracted. In such management conditions, the relations typical of the authoritarian style are formed among the members of the activity team who seek to escape individually or as a group. Indifference, mutual hatred, "unkindness" appear not only towards the management employee, but also towards each other. Everyone works only under the orders given by the immediate supervisor, and if such instructions are not given or given late, they stop work.

This style of management leads to work stoppages and impunity. This management style forces employees to form informal groups within the team for collective protection from the manager's incompetence. As a result, in the behavior of employees, a mood like "find what's in me", depression occurs, and the desire to enjoy other things and factors that are not related to work increases.

In the democratic (collegial) style of management, the manager also makes decisions himself, but prefers to influence subordinates by persuasion, develops decisions together with employees. This style of leadership believes that people who are treated like animals (authoritarian style) become stubborn and stubborn. For this reason, such a manager refrains from imposing his will on employees through administrative methods, using group discussions and encouraging subordinates to be active in decision-making.

It is very difficult to be an employee in a democratic management style. First of all, a management employee should have a deep knowledge of psychology and management in order to successfully apply a measure of influence to a specific person in a specific situation. In the second place, it is necessary for him to have a highly stable emotional passion and the ability to adapt his behavior.

A manager working in a **liberal style** entrusts the development and adoption of decisions to his subordinates, giving them complete freedom, leaving only the function of authority. The leader of this category is engaged in external relations and believes that it is possible to fully entrust the team with solving the internal life issues of the activity. He is slow in performing management functions, afraid of conflicts, usually accepts decisions suggested by the team and is ready to "swim with the flow", even if these decisions do not correspond to his personal vision.

Liberal management employees strive to establish good friendly relations with their employees. A friendly relationship, care, attention will lead to the same response from employees and many issues will be resolved without too much trouble. The disadvantage of the liberal style is that the sphere of management is very close to the employee and subordinates. Sometimes this interval is not there at all, and this limits the possibility of applying many methods of management. This style is often called "Apathy" because the methods used by the manager are ineffective in solving many problems. Usually, in a liberal style of management, the team is often divided into informal groups that promote a leader who seeks to use the power voluntarily given by the manager for his own benefit.

Results and discussion. Leadership styles are the most necessary and basic element of management activity and depend on the individual characteristics of the leader. None of the mentioned methods can claim universality and application in arbitrary conditions. Therefore, one of the important qualities of a leader is the ability to use different methods and apply them based on different situations and conditions. Leaders should consider a number of identified factors when choosing one or another method.

1. Situation (stress, calm undefined). For example, in tight time situations, the authoritarian style is justified.

2. Assignment (according to the specific structure). When performing complex tasks, it is necessary to involve experts, organize roundtable discussions, and democratic (collegial) style is lacking in this.

3. Group (gender, age, stability of its members). It is appropriate to choose a democratic or (in a creative team, a creative approach to completing tasks) liberal style for a friendly team interested in the performance of tasks.

Conclusion. The formation of management activity styles is based to a certain extent on the leader's living and working conditions (such as socio-economic conditions in the country, management activity environment, etc.) develops.

Therefore, every leader and employee working in this great country should be able to demonstrate the qualities of selflessness, perfect humanity, and patriotism for this dear country. We would like to ask all leaders and employees of our country that we are all responsible for the development of this country. So, since the future of our country depends on us, let's all come together and sincerely and conscientiously contribute to the development of our country with all our strength, all our skills, all our knowledge!

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